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Performance dependence of GPU accelerated sparse
linear system solvers on the finite element mesh
structure in micromagnetic simulations

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Performance dependence of GPU accelerated sparse linear system solvers on the finite element mesh structure in micromagnetic simulations

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Dresden, den 9.10.2020

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Abstract

In this work, the relation between the sparsity patterns of sparse matrices created through FEM discretization of a Poisson's equation problem and the performance of sparse linear system solvers working on them has been investigated. Six representative mesh geometries from the realm of micromagnetic simulations are selected and scaled in resolution and thus also in the number of unknowns in the sparse linear system, to look into the scaling behaviour of the solvers. Various concrete solver implementations are benchmarked against these specimens on three different hardware platforms: CPU, consumer GPU and professional GPU. To gain further insight these benchmarks are also conducted on the same specimen represented in reduced (single) floating point precision. As a microbenchmark the performance of sparse matrix vector multiplications on the different platforms is recorded and put into relation to the solvers overall performance.

By characterizing the specimen matrices through the mean distance of each nonzero element to its nearest nonzero neighbor, a novel metric is introduced which can accurately distinguish between matrices with fundamentally different sparsity patterns.

A modern solver configuration is identified which offers significant performance gains compared to legacy implementations across all specimen. It is found that the sparse matrix characterization metric can be applied to judge on which matrices the use of a more expensive professional GPU will have the highest return on investment. In the same way, this discriminator can also be applied to choose an appropriate sparse matrix vector multiplication routine for a specific matrix.

Kurzfassung

In dieser Arbeit wurde die Beziehung zwischen den Besetzungsmustern dünnbesetzter Matrizen, welche die FEM-Diskretisierung eines Poissonsgleichungsproblems darstellen, und der Leistung von Anwendungen zum Lösen linearer Gleichungssysteme untersucht. Sechs repräsentative Geometrien aus dem Bereich der mikromagnetischen Simulationen wurden ausgewählt und in der Auflösung skaliert, und damit auch in der Anzahl der Unbekannten in den linearen Gleichungssystemen, um das Skalierungsverhalten der Lösungsalgorithmen zu untersuchen. Verschiedene konkrete Implementierungen werden anhand dieser Beispielmatrizen auf drei verschiedenen Hardware-Plattformen verglichen: auf CPU, auf einer GPU für den Heimgebrauch und einer GPU für den professionellen Einsatz. Diese Messungen werden auch auf den selben Matrizen in reduzierter (single precision) Fließkomma-Präzision durchgeführt, um weitere Einsichten über die Limitierungen der Plattformen zu gewinnen. Als Microbenchmark wird die Leistung von Sparse-Matrix-Vektormultiplikationen auf den verschiedenen Plattformen aufgezeichnet und mit der generellen Leistungsfähigkeit der Lösungsalgorithmen in Beziehung gesetzt.

Durch die Charakterisierung der Beispielmatrizen durch den mittleren Abstand jedes Nichtnulleintrags zu seinem dichtestem Nachbarn, wird eine neue Metrik eingeführt, die zwischen Matrizen mit grundlegend verschiedenen Besetzungsmustern unterscheiden kann.

Es wird eine moderne Löser-Konfiguration identifiziert, die über alle Beispielmatrizen hinweg signifikante Leistungssteigerungen im Vergleich zu älteren Implementierungen bietet. Die eingeführte Charakterisierungsmetrik kann verwendet werden, um zu beurteilen, auf welchen Matrizen die Verwendung von teuren professionellen GPUs den größten Leistungsgewinn bietet. Der gleiche Ansatz kann auch bei der Auswahl einer geeigneten Matrix-Vektor-Multiplikationsroutine Anwendung finden, um basierend auf dem Besetzungsmuster in einer konkreten Matrix den passenden Algorithmus zu wählen.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Micromagnetic simulations

Magnetism research has benefited our society and especially information technologies greatly, one of the most prominent discoveries being the giant magnetoresistance (GMR) for which the Nobel prize was awarded in 2007 to Albert Fert and Peter Grünberg after they first described it in 1988 [1]. Its application to magnetic sensors allowed for significant increases in storage density on hard disk drives, fueling the advance of data-intensive applications for decades. Given its impact, GMR and related discoveries laid the foundations for the research domain of the so-called “spintronics”, which still flourishes to this day. It has been augmented by the emerging field of magnonics [2], which studies the magnetization dynamics of spin waves, which are also described as magnons, the eigen-excitations of the magnetic medium. Potential applications for this research are magnon-based logic through information transport, manipulation and storage. As a common framework, micromagnetism describes these phenomena on the intermediate scale between single atoms and a macroscopic view on the nano-to-micro second timescale [3].

In the last few decades the traditional tools of theoretical and experimental research have been expanded by simulations, which have become ubiquitous in various fields. They allow physicists to put their theories into an empirical context while they cut down on feedback latency and save on costly equipment. They offer unique insights how a theory executed in a pure, controlled environment measures up to reality, and allow for easier prediction of new phenomena. Micromagnetic research has made use of this tool since the 1970’s and massively at least from 1998 [3], as it is especially valuable in studying the microscale, picosecond phenomena at resolutions which are still inaccessible to experimental setups available today.

1.2 History of TETRAMAG

TETRAMAG was also originally started as a micromagnetic simulator in the 1990s, notable in its use of the finite element method (FEM) of discretization which allows for flexible geometries made from tetrahedra, as opposed to the simpler and less resource intensive finite difference method (FDM), which only allows for rectangular discretization. Important examples of simulation frameworks based on FDM are OOMMF [4] and MUMAX [5], which are available for free and open-source.

With the advent of affordable consumer graphics cards capable of double precision calculations, namely the NVIDIA GTX 200 series, its authors A. Kákay, E. Westphal, and R. Hertel seized the opportunity to utilize these capabilities to speed up the involved calculations by an order of magnitude without the need to rely on traditional HPC infrastructure [6]. In conjunction with the application of hierarchical matrix schemes [7] to significantly reduce the memory footprint of the simulations, these advances brought the scale of the micromagnetic simulations conducted with TETRAMAG to a new level, enabling physicists to analyze and predict new phenomena, such as the Spin-Cherenkov effect [8] – the magnetic equivalent of a sonic boom, and curvature-induced magnetochiral effects [9, 10, 11].

2 Foundations

2.1 Physics background

To study the magnetization dynamics governed by the different magnetic interactions, the micromagnetic simulator needs to solve the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation [12] of motion, which describes the time dependence of the magnetization in a given magnetic medium as a combination of precession and damping:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{M}}{dt} = \frac{-\gamma}{1 + \alpha^2} (\mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}) - \frac{\gamma\alpha}{M_s(1 + \alpha^2)} \mathbf{M} \times (\mathbf{M} \times \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}) \quad (2.1)$$

where \mathbf{M} is the magnetization vector field, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, M_s the saturation magnetization, α the phenomenological Gilbert damping constant and \mathbf{H}_{eff} the effective magnetic field.

As a necessary precursor, the \mathbf{H}_{eff} needs to be known, which is the sum of all the magnetic fields from the various internal and external sources. An important summand to that is the demagnetizing or stray field \mathbf{H}_S resulting from the magnetostatic interaction, which can be calculated [13] from the magnetic charge densities $\rho = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}$ (volume charges) and $\sigma = \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{M}$ (surface charges) as

$$\mathbf{H}_S(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{r}') \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^3} dV' + \oint_{\partial\Omega} \sigma(\mathbf{r}') \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^3} dS' \right]$$

However, the numerical solution of such a volume integral would be far too computationally expensive [6], instead the stray field is calculated as the gradient of the scalar magnetic potential U , given by the Maxwell equations. This splits the problem between two domains, inside the magnetic medium it is described by

$$\Delta U(\mathbf{r}) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2.2)$$

and outside the magnetic medium by

$$\Delta U(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad (2.3)$$

The boundary conditions between these two domains are well known, and numerical approaches to solving this problem comprised of Poisson's and Laplace's equation are available. TETRAMAG employs the hybrid finite element - boundary integral method developed by Fredkin and Koehler [14], which has the advantageous property that only the volume inside the magnetic medium needs to be discretized.

2.2 Numerical approach

As a first outlook, due to the strong correlation to the scope of this research, it has to be noted that the time integration of equation 2.1 can take up a significant portion of the total execution time in a micromagnetic simulation loop. It has been observed that selecting an appropriate integrator method based on the structure of the mesh can yield a considerable reduction in runtime. For example, Adams-Moulton formulas are used for small, regular meshes which have low stiffness, and Backward Differentiation Formulas in combination with Newton iteration for large, irregular meshes with high stiffness [15]. Continuing from this observation, within this work this approach shall be applied to the solution of Poisson's equation as given in 2.2, preferentially based on quantifiable characteristics and benchmark results.

Given that it is a commonly studied problem with applications far beyond the scope of micromagnetism, solving a problem given in the form of Poisson's equation is well studied, and even used as an introductory example in the literature [16].

TETRAMAG uses the Finite Element Method (FEM) to discretize the problem and reduce the analytical complexity. First, the desired specimen geometry is discretized by constructing it from tetrahedra, which form the volume elements. By approximating the problem in each volume element by a local, linear shape function on every node of the mesh, it is expressed as a set of linear equations with a number of degrees of freedom equal to the number of nodes in the mesh. Written as a matrix A , we arrive at the core problem formulation we are going to tackle from here on:

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}$$

The vector \mathbf{b} is commonly known as the right-hand-side vector, and \mathbf{x} is called the vector of unknowns, or after the system has been solved for it, the solution vector. Notably, many of the coefficients in \mathbf{A} are zero, since only nodes which are connected by a vertex will result in entries in \mathbf{A} .

2.2.1 Sparse linear system solvers

Solving linear systems is a basic exercise in calculus, and a multitude of algorithms have been designed to solve these problems. Sparse linear systems, although they are a subset in that space, pose unique challenges as they are not as accessible to traditional solver schemes, both in the way the matrix is represented (see 2.4), as well as due to the comparatively high number of degrees of freedom enabled by the sparsity. Lastly, some algebraic transformations such as the inverse are prohibitively expensive both in terms of time and memory, as they would yield dense matrices of the same dimensions as intermediate results. Nevertheless, sparse linear system solvers have been extensively studied due to their importance in the domain of FDM and FEM analysis, and various algorithms have been developed.

2.2.1.1 Direct solvers

Like in the well-known Gauss algorithm one approach to solving a linear system is to transform it in a way that one ends up with a system in which at least one row of A contains only a single coefficient and is zero everywhere else, allowing the corresponding unknown to be immediately extracted. By extension, if that unknown appears in a row which has only coefficients for already deducted unknowns, its corresponding unknown can again be extracted. For a given triangular matrix, which only contains nonzero coefficients

on one side from the diagonal, in the lower-left or upper-right, this process is called forward or backward substitution, respectively. Motivated by this, there is a class of solver algorithms which factorize or decompose A into a product where at least one factor is a triangular matrix, and then solve the linear system by chaining forward or backwards substitutions from there. Since the number of steps necessary to perform the necessary transformations and substitutions is pre-determined by the number of degrees of freedom and thus finite, methods of this type are called “direct”. They typically operate in a binary fashion, as they either come up with a solution which is – within floating-point representation error – analytically correct or fail completely, based on the attributes of the linear system. Some methods can also take advantage of certain matrix properties, such as symmetry or being positive definite.

Some of these algorithms also lend themselves to sparse linear systems, as long as they avoid fill-in, that is replacing former zeros in the sparse matrix with new coefficients, which could reduce the sparsity to much and make storage and further calculations infeasible. Thus, additional steps such as reordering or splitting calculations into a symbolic and a numerical part are required [16]. Most notable here are the LU, QR and Cholesky decomposition approaches. Benchmark results for the latter two are presented in 4.4.

2.2.2 Iterative solvers

In opposition to the direct solvers, iterative approaches don’t have a predetermined runtime and instead try to converge towards a sufficiently accurate solution by incremental improvements on an initial guess of the solution vector. Most notably here are methods from the Krylov subspace family, which are able to avoid expensive matrix-matrix operations by repeated matrix-vector operations, such as:

$$A(A\mathbf{b}) = A^2\mathbf{b}$$

These powers of the matrix A are then used to approximate its inverse through a polynomial [16], which is otherwise also a prohibitively expensive operation.

GMRES, the generalized minimum residual method, is one of the most prominent representatives in this class of solvers, as well as algorithms based on the biconjugate gradient method such as TETRAMAG’s LINBCG and AMGX’s BICGSTAB. Furthermore, these solvers are nowadays commonly used in combination with preconditioners, which aim to increase both efficiency and robustness of the iterative solvers. This is achieved by transforming the linear system into one which has the same solution, but is more accessible to the solvers. A few notable examples include the Block-Jacobi and (algebraic) multigrid preconditioners, the latter are especially noteworthy as they lend the name to the AMGX library, and are especially well positioned to tackle large problems by employing a divide-and-conquer approach. However, selecting a good preconditioner-solver-combination is a difficult process and often counter-intuitive. To quote Saad [16]:

Finding a good preconditioner to solve a given sparse linear system is often viewed as a combination of art and science. Theoretical results are rare and some methods work surprisingly well, often despite expectations.

The benchmarking results for a subset of the mentioned solvers and preconditioners are presented in 4.2.

2.3 GPU architectures

A Graphics Processing Unit differs from a traditional CPU most significantly in that it is foremost designed as an array processor, operating on data governed by the Single-Instruction-Multiple-Data (SIMD) paradigm. This enables them to achieve much higher operations throughput than traditional CPUs, since thousands of compute units process data in parallel. However, when it comes to General Purpose GPU (GPGPU) programming, preparing a problem in a way that it is accessible to SIMD-style processing is usually very difficult and introduces overheads of its own, often partially negating the potential performance gains compared to the raw numbers. Within the scope of the research conducted here, the most important consequence of the typical GPU architecture is that for high utilization and thus efficiency, enough data to process needs to be available without memory latencies stalling the processing units.

2.4 Sparse matrix storage schemes

A matrix is called sparse, if a significant portion of its elements are zero. In our context this also applies to elements which are in magnitude small enough that they can be ignored in further calculations which have limited precision anyhow. Such elements as well as zeros don't need to be stored in memory, thus potentially saving orders of magnitudes of storage space. This allows much larger problems to be represented on the available computation hardware.

However, if the zero valued elements are discarded, it's no longer possible to implicitly deduce the location of the nonzero elements in the matrix from their position in memory, and vice versa. Additional structural information has to be stored, for which a number of storage schemes have been developed. The most common as well as the ones relevant to this research are described below. For the following a square matrix of dimensions $N \times N$ will be referred to, for which nnz will denote the number of nonzero elements in the matrix. In terms of a sparse linear system, N is also called the number of degrees of freedom or number of unknowns.

2.4.1 Coordinate format: COO

Intuitively, one might consider saving all nnz nonzero elements as triples along with their row and column indices. This is also called the COO format, typically implemented by storing three vectors of length nnz , which contain the data, row and column index for each element, which is identified by its offset within these vectors. Additionally it is usually required (e.g. by CUSPARSE) that the elements are ordered first by row and then by column.

2.4.2 Compressed Sparse Row format: CSR

The CSR scheme as given by the CUSPARSE documentation [17] stores the sparse matrix in three vectors, one of length $N + 1$, and two of length nnz : All row-offsets (the memory locations where a row starts) and the end of the last row in the first, and the latter two contain all the nonzero values and their column indices. All elements have again to be ordered, by row first, then by column.

The equivalent *Compressed Sparse Column* (CSC) scheme is defined by saving the nonzero elements in column-first order and replacing the row-offsets with column-offsets accordingly, saving the row indices separately.

2.4.3 Row-Indexed Sparse storage scheme: RIS

The sparse matrix representation used in the original, CPU-only TETRAMAG implementation was proposed by Press et al. in the “Numerical Recipes in C” [18] as the *row-indexed sparse storage mode*. It is also called the *New Yale format* [19] or *modified sparse row format* [16].

It consists of two vectors, each of length $nnz + 1$, with the vector containing row-offsets and column indices commonly called ija , and the actual values in vector sa . Vector ija contains pointers to the start of all rows in order and the end of the last row in the first $N + 1$ fields, followed by the column indices of all off-diagonal nonzero elements. The vector sa contains all elements of the diagonal in the first N fields, followed by an arbitrary delimiter value for alignment, and then row-by-row all off-diagonal elements. Thus, the whole diagonal is easily accessible, while the storage space potentially wasted on storing explicit zeros in the diagonal part is usually negligible.

2.5 Sparse matrix vector multiplication

A typical sparse matrix vector multiplication (SpMV) of the form Ax can be computed in parallel [16], especially well if the matrix is represented in a scheme with directly accessible rows, such as CSR, since then each component of the result can be calculated independently as the scalar product between the corresponding row vector and the right hand side vector. Due to the low number of arithmetic operations per accessed matrix datum (one multiplication and one addition per non-zero element of the matrix), this calculation is usually bandwidth-bound.

Furthermore, depending on the specific sparsity pattern of a given sparse matrix, the number and distribution of non-zero elements per row may vary and thus amplify the bandwidth constraint through non-coalesced memory accesses. Further inefficiency might be introduced by uneven distribution of the workload, e.g. if a whole row is assigned to each available compute unit. These problems can be addressed by padding and reordering, to achieve aligned access and even distribution of the workload between the available resources [20].

2.5.1 TETRAMAG SpMV approach

TETRAMAG stores a reordered representation of the sparse matrix in device memory, to address potentially misaligned memory access and distribute workload between threads evenly. This incurs a larger storage overhead due to the necessary additional structure information, which has to be stored, such as the per-row number of non-zero elements, which is not implicitly given via the sa vector anymore. This reordering is also computationally expensive, and would have to be redone if any changes to the sparsity pattern of the matrix were to happen.

The TETRAMAG CUDA kernel most commonly used implements the following composite operation on the dense vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , a dense vector of weights \mathbf{w} , the sparse matrix \mathbf{A} and an integer boolean β :

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{w} \circ (\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x}) + \beta \mathbf{y} \text{ for } \beta \in \{0, 1\}$$

The weights \mathbf{w} are applied by element-wise multiplication, i.e. in a Hadamard product.

2.5.2 cuSPARSE SpMV algorithms

The vendor library CUSPARSE [17] (in version 10.2) provides two algorithm choices for multiplying a matrix in *CSR* format with a dense vector. As is common for implementations, the provided interface performs not only a matrix-vector multiplication, but the following composite operation, with α and β being scalar factors, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} dense vectors and \mathbf{A} the sparse matrix:

$$\mathbf{y} = \alpha \text{op}(\mathbf{A}) \cdot \mathbf{x} + \beta \mathbf{y}$$

Where $\text{op}(\mathbf{A})$ can be chosen to be \mathbf{A} , the transposed matrix \mathbf{A}^T or the conjugate transposed matrix \mathbf{A}^H . `CSR MV_ALG1` is the default algorithm, `CSR MV_ALG2` is recommended for use with irregular matrices. Due to the proprietary, closed-source nature of the vendor library no further implementation details are provided, and it has been shown that it is outperformed across a variety of benchmarking matrices by novel approaches such as Adaptive-CSR [21], PCSR [20] and IPCSR [22].

3 Evaluation methods

3.1 Case studies

To study the performance dependence of SpMV routines and sparse linear system solvers on FEM discretized meshes, a selection of typical geometries in micromagnetic simulations was prepared. Selection criteria were ease of scalability while covering a wide range of regular, structured meshes through partially structured meshes up to fully unstructured, irregular meshes.

From the selected geometries meshes were created through different versions of GMSH [23], as changes in its meshing algorithms result in different regularity patterns, some of which are undesirable for micromagnetic simulations. Furthermore, newer versions of GMSH introduced modern CAD-style geometry definitions with the OPENCASCADE backend, which enables seamless meshing of geometries which formerly had to be constructed from several subvolumes, such as the sphere. The version of GMSH used for each case study is included with its script listing in the appendices from B.1 onward.

Regularity was achieved by constructing the desired geometry by layer-wise extrusion, irregular meshing is happening if GMSH is not provided such structural information, but only the outlines of the desired geometry. As highly regular meshes the *μMAG standard problem #4 thin film strip* and a *regular cuboid* were chosen. Mixed-regularity meshes were produced for a *moebius strip* and a *disk*. Completely irregular meshes are studied through a *sphere* geometry and an *irregular cuboid*.

All mesh types were scaled in their resolution by varying the characteristic length between nodes to cover a range of about 10^4 up to over 10^6 nodes, which corresponds to the degrees of freedom in the linearized system which will need to be solved. The characteristic length parameters used to achieve this scaling can be found in table B.1.

μMAG standard problem #4 thin film strip

This thin film strip is a cuboid with dimensions of 500:125:3, see listing B.1 for the GMSH script. However, the number of layers along the shortest dimension is fixed at three layers of nodes, i.e. two layers of volume elements. For characteristic length significantly smaller or larger than 1 this leads to highly elongated or broad volume elements.

It is part of the well-established set of standard problems published by the NIST μMAG group [24], and has been used to verify the solutions calculated by the original TETRAMAG implementation and calibrate its iterative algorithm's parameters, such as convergence criteria.

Regularly meshed cuboid

A cuboid with dimensions of 500:125:50, with evenly structured layers across all dimensions, its GMSH script is listed at B.2. An example matrix resulting from this type of mesh is shown in figure 3.2a.

(b) Regular cuboid

(c) Disk

(d) Moebius strip

(e) Sphere

(f) Irregular cuboid

Figure 3.1: Mesh pictures of the lowest-resolution specimens of all case studies.

Moebius strip

A twisted cuboid attached to its own face surface to form the typical loop of a moebius strip. Since it consists of warped 3D body there are two surfaces, the wide (60 units) top and bottom surface as well as the thinner (25 units) inner and outer edge surface. Due to its length the GMSH script could not be included here.

Disk

The base circle is meshed irregularly in 2D, extruding these along the height dimension results in a mesh with mixed regularity across the different dimensions. It has a radius of 50 and a height of 20 units, see listing B.3 for the GMSH script. The disk is a noticeable example here, since it is a commonly studied object, e.g. in the form of wires, but fully regular meshing by extruding a radius would lead to a large number of interconnected nodes in the radial centre, which has to be avoided.

Sphere

A sphere or ball with a radius of 50 units, its GMSH script is listed at B.4. The GMSH OPENCASCADE features are used to create a homogeneous, continuous sphere.

Irregularly meshed cuboid

A cuboid of the same dimensions as before in 3.1, however the GMSH meshing algorithm is given no layer information to produce a structured mesh, thus producing an irregular mesh for the whole volume. The GMSH script is available as listing B.5. An example matrix resulting from this type of mesh is shown in figure 3.2b.

Figure 3.2: Sparsity pattern visualizations for two case study examples at extremely low resolutions of $\approx 4 \cdot 10^2$ nodes, which are hence not part of the benchmarked specimens. Black pixels represent nonzero elements, white pixels are zeros.

3.2 Benchmarking procedures

Since the scope of this research is to study the performance of sparse linear system solvers specifically in application to FEM micromagnetic simulations, it was desirable to design the benchmarking approach as close to a real-world simulation loop as possible. This includes using the actual sparse linear systems resulting from the concrete physical problems as described in 2.1, as well as a realistic application of these solvers in a looped, long-running setting. To achieve this, an integrated benchmarking loop was

designed, which would both fulfill the above requirements in terms of realism, as well as being able to provide statistically significant results in a reproducible manner.

3.2.1 Preparations

After designing and meshing the specimens in 3.1 using GMSH, they were prepared for evaluation by the TETRAMAG preprocessing pipeline. Most importantly, this includes transforming the given mesh and physical problem, i.e. differential equation, into a sparse linear system represented by a sparse matrix by the Finite Element method. The sparsity patterns of two such matrices are shown in figure 3.2. Since calculating these representations is quite time consuming, the resulting sparse matrices are cached by saving them to disk. All values in these matrices are real numbers and represented using IEEE 754 double precision (64 bits).

To perform a single benchmarking run, the sparse linear system chosen to evaluate is loaded from disk. If applicable, it is then converted into the required sparse matrix format by converter routines between COO, CSR and RIS written for this research, and transferred to the GPU. As it is constant for a given mesh, no further transfers or updates to it are necessary later on.

3.2.2 Integrated benchmarking

Inside the benchmarking loop, first the right hand side vector, given by equation 2.2, is calculated from the magnetization in the magnetic medium, which is initialized to the same values across all specimen. If necessary, the right hand side vector is then uploaded to the GPU memory.

After making sure all potentially asynchronous operations have finished, a time stamp is taken to mark the start of a single solver run. The solver implementation is then tasked with solving the sparse linear system, afterwards again all asynchronous operations are synced and a timestamp to mark the end of the run is taken.

The solution that has been computed and its accompanying metrics are downloaded from the GPU, the solution is used to calculate a residual independently from any implementation. All performance metrics taken are both logged for each run, as well as added to an average for each metric, where applicable.

Finally, to present the solvers with a realistic range of computational difficulty in the sparse linear systems while avoiding having to implement a complete, physically correct micromagnetic simulation, the magnetization of the magnetic medium – a unit vector field – is randomly varied by adding up to $\pm 10^{-2}$ in each dimension, in a uniform distribution, and lastly the magnetization is re-normalized. This loop is typically repeated 1000 times to acquire statistically stable and reproducible results.

3.2.3 Implementation specific remarks

As a rather diverse set of solver and related frameworks are covered in this research, some require specific details to be discussed in depth.

3.2.3.1 TETRAMAG LINBCG

The original TETRAMAG implementation of a biconjugate gradient iterative sparse linear system solver is available both for CPU and CUDA GPUs. The application supports OPENMP parallelization, however

that was disabled for the CPU versions to ensure comparability with other CPU solver implementations which don't offer any multithreading. Both the CPU and GPU version use the RIS matrix storage scheme described in 2.4.3. However, the GPU implementation relies on a reordered memory representation of that format to utilize coalesced memory access from the GPU.

Their convergence criterion is based on a normalized or relative residual of the form

$$\frac{|\mathbf{Ax} - \mathbf{b}|}{|\mathbf{x}|}$$

3.2.3.2 CUSOLVER

The CUSOLVER library [25] offers direct solvers, running on CUDA GPUs, using the CSR matrix storage scheme from 2.4.2. The solver routines based on QR decomposition `cusolverSpDcsrslsvqr` and Cholesky factorization `cusolverSpDcsrslsvchol` were chosen due to the ease of applying them to our specimens. As they are direct solvers, they don't employ any kind of convergence criterion, and there are no tuning parameters. Due to the excessively long runtimes these solvers require, the number of solutions acquired per specimen had to be reduced to 10, as opposed to 1000 for all other solvers.

3.2.3.3 AMGX

The GPU-focused AMGX iterative solver library [26, 27] also offers a host-mode, however only a subset of solver and related routines is actually implemented for CPU, and only run single-threaded there. It also uses the CSR storage scheme.

It offers several options to determine convergence, to match the quality and approach of the original TETRAMAG LINBCG implementation as closely as possible, the absolute L2-norm of the residual was used:

$$|\mathbf{Ax} - \mathbf{b}|$$

Unfortunately, as of the time this research was done, the AMGX documentation [26] had not been updated since 2017, and a number of features – including some used here – are not documented at all.

3.2.4 Quality and comparability of solutions

Since all solutions provided by the different implementations are of a numerical nature, they are inherently of limited accuracy. This is especially a concern for iterative algorithms, as they need to establish some kind of convergence criterion to decide if a “good enough” solution has been found or further refinement is required.

As the original TETRAMAG implementation has been extensively validated on standard problems and by experimental results, it was used to establish a baseline quality expectation, which the other implementations had to match or exceed. The resulting mean residuals across 1000 solutions for all iterative solvers evaluated here are shown in figure 3.3, besides minor variance due to randomization and stochastic effects the baseline LINBCG residuals are an upper limit on all other solvers' mean residuals. Furthermore, spot checks were performed to independently assure that the solutions provided by different solver frameworks are physically valid by examining the resulting potential and comparing it to established results.

Figure 3.3: Mean absolute and relative residuals across all 1000 solutions for all specimens. The left-right grouping of case studies is arbitrary and only meant to improve visual distinction. The LINBCG results, which are connected by the dashed line, were set as the upper limit, i.e. convergence criteria, for the other solvers. The resulting residuals of those are signified by the white markers overlaid on top of the case study symbol.

In the course of this research it became noticeable that quantifying a “good enough” solution in a more consistent way is a promising avenue for further research, since the current approach is prone to overshooting the actually, physically necessary residual and thus wasting resources on overly accurate solutions. Higher residual requirements would lead to earlier convergence and thus to shorter runtimes.

3.2.5 Micro benchmarking

To study the isolated performance of sparse matrix vector multiplications across different implementations the time to perform 10^5 such multiplications was measured. For each specimen, the sparse matrix and the vector used were kept constant. To measure raw throughput of the different implementations, no synchronization of asynchronous operations in between the single multiplications was forced, and only the total run time across all the multiplications is recorded.

3.3 Benchmarking hardware and environment

As the focus of this research proposal is on consumer-grade hardware, the main benchmarking environment was an enthusiast workstation machine.

To give some insight what advantages a professional HPC environment might offer, a subset of the measurements was repeated on the HZDR HPC cluster.

3.3.1 Consumer-grade workstation setup

The main benchmarking environment was composed of a NVIDIA Titan Xp in the Jedi Order Collector's Edition, which is based on NVIDIA's Pascal architecture (CUDA Compute Capability 6.1). This GPU was accompanied by an Intel Core i5 6600K with 16 GiB of GDDR4 RAM on an Intel Z170 chipset motherboard. The total cost of this system at the time the components were bought between 2016 and 2017 comes up to about 2000€.

The operating system in use was an Arch Linux, kernel 5.8, with the proprietary NVIDIA driver of version 450 and CUDA version 10.2. The host compiler used was gcc 8.4.

3.3.2 HPC cluster setup

The HZDR HPC cluster offers nodes with four NVIDIA Tesla P100 SXM2 GPUs, which are also based on NVIDIA's Pascal architecture (CUDA Compute Capability 6.0). As part of the Tesla lineup of NVIDIA products they represent the "professional" equivalent of the Titan Xp within that generation of cards.

These cards are installed on a dual-socket board with two Intel Xeon Gold 6136 CPUs and 384 GiB of DDR4 RAM. Since multi-GPU applications are not within the scope of this research, for all measurements a single GPU along with 4 CPU cores and 16 GiB of RAM were allocated. All CPU-only solver benchmarks were also run as cluster jobs on the same nodes, with 8 cores and 32 GiB of RAM. Bought in 2017, the cost of such a quarter of a node amounts to ca. 8000€. However, this includes the necessary hardware to run in a datacenter environment (especially network interfaces), as well as NVLink capabilities which won't be utilized here.

The cluster nodes are running CentOS 7.4 with a version 3.10 Linux kernel. The installed NVIDIA driver was of version 440, CUDA version 10.0 was used along with gcc 8.2.

Benchmarks were also conducted on the Tesla V100 cards available on the cluster, however no deeper analysis of these results has been conducted. For future reference and as a baseline to performance expectations, it is compared against the other cards in the appended figures A.2 through A.5, and a chart of the total runtimes on all three cards used here is provided in A.6.

3.3.3 GPU comparison - Titan Xp vs P100

	Titan Xp	Tesla P100 SXM2
CUDA Cores	3840 ⁱ	3584 ⁱ
Base Clock	1404 MHz ⁱ	1328 MHz ⁱ
Boost Clock	1582 MHz ⁱⁱ	1480 MHz ⁱ
Memory Type	GDDR5X ⁱⁱ	HBM2 ⁱⁱ
Memory Capacity	12 GiB ⁱ	16 GiB ⁱ
Memory Bandwidth	547 GB/s ⁱⁱ	732 GB/s ⁱⁱ
Single-Precision Performance	12.1 TFLOPS ⁱⁱⁱ	10.6 TFLOPS ⁱⁱ
Double-Precision Performance	0.38 TFLOPS ⁱⁱⁱ	5.3 TFLOPS ⁱⁱ
Max Power Consumption	250 W ⁱⁱ	300 W ⁱⁱ

Table 3.1: Specifications comparison of the GPUs used

On first glance, the Titan Xp offers higher compute throughput in single precision FLOPS due to a higher number of CUDA cores in combination with a higher base and boost clock. However, since there is little use for double precision FLOPs in consumer applications, it is severely lacking in those, as the ratio of single precision vs double precision FLOP throughput per multiprocessor in the Titan Xp is 32:1¹. With a similar single precision FLOP performance, but a ratio of 2:1, the P100 significantly outperforms the Titan Xp in double precision FLOPS. Furthermore, the P100 offers much higher memory bandwidth and the advanced HBM2 memory architecture.

3.4 Sparse matrix characterization

The discretization and linearization of a geometry’s mesh and the physical problem to solve lead to a unique sparse matrix for each geometry and equation.

To investigate the performance dependence of the sparse linear system solvers on the FEM mesh structure and its resulting sparse matrix in a way which could potentially be used for automated optimization decisions, quantifiable criteria are needed. However, due to the difficulties that arise when performing complex operations on sparse matrices based on its representation in memory, such a metric should ideally also be simple and inexpensive to compute on the common storage schemes.

Such metrics for sparse matrices are not well established. Performance analysis is usually done based on a selection of sample matrices, e.g. from the SuiteSparse Matrix Collection² (formerly the University of Florida Sparse Matrix Collection). Such samples are mainly characterized by a few qualitative properties, such as the underlying differential equation and attributes like symmetry or being positive-definite. Quantitative characterization is at most provided by listing the sparsity or condition number. However, like in the comparison of Krylov subspace preconditioned solvers by Ghai et al. [29] or the AMGX performance verification paper by Naumov et al. [27], this makes it difficult to put the matrices in relation to each other and draw conclusions for future applications or on how the solvers would scale with the sparse linear system’s size.

ⁱAccording to the output of `nvidia-smi` on the benchmark systems

ⁱⁱAccording to NVIDIA’s promotional websites on the Titan Xp and the Tesla P100

ⁱⁱⁱAccording to independent benchmark numbers at gpuzoo.com and partially confirmed on NVIDIA’s official blog

¹According to the NVIDIA CUDA programming guide’s [28] table on arithmetic throughput.

²<https://sparse.tamu.edu/>

3.4.1 Density

Characterizing a sparse matrix is typically foremost done by calculating its density ρ or its complementary value, the sparsity as $1 - \rho$, which are the ratio between the number of nonzero or zero elements and the total number of elements. For a given matrix with dimensions of $M \times N$ with nnz nonzero elements:

$$\rho = \frac{nnz}{M \cdot N}$$

Since both the dimensions as well as nnz are usually already known, this is trivial to calculate.

However, this simple measure omits all information about the sparsity pattern, general matrix structure, and regularity. Different matrices with the same density could have completely different distributions or patterns of nonzero elements. Given the dependence of efficient GPU parallelization on evenly distributed workloads and coalesced memory access, its informational value is limited.

3.4.2 Nonzero elements per row

Simple parallelization approaches to e.g. CSR sparse matrix vector multiplication might be highly susceptible to a high variance in the number of nonzero elements per row, as row-wise parallelization is easy to implement, but the resulting workload per compute unit might be very unevenly distributed this way. Sophisticated algorithms addressing this will also incur higher overhead due to reordering and redistributing partial rows.

Given that the studied matrices are representations of connections between the nodes in the corresponding mesh, the number of nonzero elements per row can be expected to give some insight into the hierarchy of node connections.

3.4.3 Mean distance to nearest nonzero neighbour

Regular meshes typically lead to matrix representations in which most nonzero elements are clustered along the main or secondary diagonals, which means most have other nonzero elements nearby. The sparsity pattern of an example of such a matrix resulting from a highly regular mesh is given in figure 3.2a. Irregular meshes present more uniform distributions of nonzero elements, spreading them out across the whole matrix, as is visible in figure 3.2b.

To quantify these patterns, the mean distance from each nonzero element to its nearest nonzero neighbour can be calculated as the L2 norm in the index space. So for a matrix with all nonzero elements contiguously on a diagonal this value would be $\sqrt{2}$, and for a matrix with all nonzero elements in rectangular clusters exactly 1. Given the relatively low densities of all selected specimen, matrices with a significant number of nonzero elements outside any such structures should exhibit much higher values.

For this work a simple brute-force, single-threaded approach to calculate this value for matrices in the COO representation was implemented. For a given nonzero element the immediate left or right neighbor within the same row gives an upper limit to the distance. From here, the search iterates first through the rows above upwards and then through the rows below downwards, updating the upper limit to the distance whenever a closer nonzero neighbor is found. Once more rows than the current upper limit have been checked, the search can stop for the current direction, once that happened for both directions the true value has been found.

Already this naive implementation of a search concluded in under an hour even for the largest specimens, and could easily be parallelized since the above procedure can be done for each nonzero element at the same time, requiring only a simple reduction to finally acquire the mean. Adapting it to the CSR format should also pose no problems, as it only requires out-of-order access to the rows of the matrix. Transposing the procedure, essentially replacing rows with columns, should then work equally well on the CSC format.

4 Results

4.1 Mesh analysis

4.1.1 Densities

The density for all meshes studied here is shown in figure 4.1, as it was defined in 3.4. All geometries display the same basic trend of rapidly decreasing density at higher resolution. With a uniform slope of ≈ -1 in the log-log plot no distinguishing features are evident. This also shows that the densities roughly follow a $const/N$ relationship. As expected, the densities of the matrices do not lend themselves to discriminate between sparsity patterns.

Figure 4.1: Densities ρ of all case study specimens.

4.1.2 Nonzero elements per row

To expand on that relationship, figure 4.2 shows the mean nonzero elements per matrix row, i.e. per degree of freedom in our linear system, nnz/N ; which is the same as $\rho \times N$.

This representation of the matrices shows much more distinguishing features than the plain densities, especially the μ MAG #4 specimens show a distinct behaviour of a nearly constant value for the larger specimens, whereas all other mesh types exhibit a clear increase with increasing resolution.

This increase mainly reflects the change in volume to surface ratio for increasing resolutions, according to the square-cube law, which is not applicable to the μ MAG #4 thin film in the same way since it's ratio of surface to volume nodes is basically fixed, as the number of layers does not increase in one dimension.

Figure 4.2: Mean number of nonzero elements per row for all case study specimens.

4.1.3 Mean distances to nearest nonzero neighbor

Developed as a measure to specifically characterize the sparsity patterns in terms of potential clustering opposed to a more uniform distribution, the mean distance to the nearest nonzero neighbor offers an immediate insight, as is evident from figure 4.3. For a given number of degrees of freedom larger than $\approx 3 \cdot 10^4$, the case studies are easily distinguishable by this measure.

Figure 4.3: Mean distances to nearest neighbor across all nonzero elements of all case study specimens.

Furthermore, the order of their associated values lines up with the so far only qualitatively described degree of structure within a mesh: High values for the unstructured irregular cuboid and sphere, which also appear to converge for high resolutions as one would expect given that the influence of highly connected nodes inside the volume should outweigh the diminishing contributions from surface nodes, which are the only ones where the irregular cuboid and the sphere topologically differ. The semi-regular moebius strip and disk fall into an intermediate range, and the highly structured regular cuboid and μ MAG #4 thin film strip exhibit very low numbers which are also not increasing with resolution.

4.2 Iterative solver results

Due to the successful heritage of TETRAMAG, iterative, Krylov subspace method based solvers were the main focus while evaluating and selecting modern solver candidates.

4.2.1 Baseline performance

To establish a baseline for further comparisons, figure 4.4 shows the performance of the original TETRAMAG LINBCG solver across all specimens, both for executing it single-threaded on CPU and highly parallelized on GPU. As has been described by its authors [6], there is a significant speedup for the GPU version, which is even more pronounced than 10 years ago due to the increasing performance gap between single CPU cores and the matured GPGPU devices available.

Figure 4.4: Run times and their ratios for all specimen for 1000 solutions with TETRAMAG LINBCG on CPU vs on the Titan Xp GPU.

4.2.2 Recreation of original approach in current day framework

To get a first reference point as to what current day sparse linear system solvers are capable of, the baseline TETRAMAG benchmarks were recreated with the AMGX BICGSTAB solver, both single-threaded on CPU as well as on GPU, the run times and their ratios are presented in figure 4.5, equivalent to figure 4.4. The configuration file for the BICGSTAB solver is available as listing C.1.

As shown in figure 4.6, the more recent implementation of BICGSTAB, using vendor libraries, is actually outperformed for the majority of specimens, only for a few of the largest ones BICGSTAB at least matches the performance of the TETRAMAG LINBCG solver.

This in contrast to the number of iterations the two algorithms require to reach convergence, as can be seen in figure 4.7. The BICGSTAB solver needs significantly fewer iterations in almost all specimen, suggesting that it is more effective at reducing the residual within a single step. On average, both solvers need a few hundred to a thousand iterations to reach convergence, loosely scaling with mesh resolution. Based on the metrics established in 4.1 there is no clear pattern for which meshes it would be beneficial to use BICGSTAB over LINBCG. However, due to the overall poor performance, these dependencies were not further investigated.

Figure 4.5: Run times and their ratios for all specimen for 1000 solutions with AMGX BICGSTAB on CPU vs on the Titan Xp GPU.

Figure 4.6: Run time ratios of LINBCG over BICGSTAB for all specimens, on the Titan Xp GPU.

Figure 4.7: Iteration number ratios of LINBCG over BICGSTAB for all specimens, on the Titan Xp GPU.

4.2.3 Maximising performance – AMG preconditioned approaches

After iterating through the cornucopia of preconditioner-solver combinations along with their various tuning parameters, an AMG preconditioned BICGSTAB configuration – from here on called PBICGSTAB – emerged as a very promising candidate, offering both a huge performance gain as well as reliable performance. Noticably, many simpler approaches, using only basic preconditioners like BLOCK_JACOBI, failed to reliably converge, rendering all potential performance gains moot. To complement this biconjugate gradient method based solver and look for potential mesh-specific performance disparities, the same preconditioning approach was applied to the AMGX GMRES solver. The AMGX configuration files for both are available as listings C.2 and C.3. To illustrate the power of the AMG preconditioning employed, it has to be noted that for all the following results the two preconditioned solvers typically converged within less than 10 iterations, one to two orders of magnitude less than the non-preconditioned LINBCG and BICGSTAB.

In figure 4.8 the run times for these solvers are compared to the LINBCG baseline run times as well as against each other. Both PBICGSTAB and GMRES outperform LINBCG significantly and consistently, however, there are clear deviations across the case studies. For both solvers, the μ MAG #4 specimens are the clear winners here, saving more than an order of magnitude in run time across all resolutions, but with diminishing results for higher resolutions. In contrast to that the regular cuboid, moebius strip and disk show increasing performance gains with increasing resolution. The irregular cuboid and sphere show a similar overall behaviour, they reach a peak performance gain just below 10^6 degrees of freedom, however at a significant offset as the sphere profits the least of all case studies.

Comparing the run times of these two favoured solvers directly, PBICGSTAB emerges as a one-size-fits-all tool to employ in a real-world application. It is only outperformed by GMRES for the highest-resolution μ MAG #4 specimens. These edge cases could easily be identified by the mean distance to nearest neighbor metric presented in 4.1, however it seems questionable if there would be a proportionate return on investment as the high-resolution μ MAG #4 specimens are not of physical interest due to their abnormally shaped volume elements.

Figure 4.8: Run time ratios between pairs of PBICGSTAB, GMRES and LINBCG for 1000 solutions on the Titan Xp GPU.

4.2.4 Single precision benchmarks

As described in 3.3, consumer and enthusiast GPUs suffer from a significant lack of double precision floating point units (FPUs). Given that all data in the sparse matrices, in the right-hand-side and also in the solution vector is stored in double precision, this poses the question – assuming that physically relevant solutions can be obtained at all – if reducing the data and the resulting calculations to single precision might result in similarly proportioned performance gains. Additionally, since the data to process is effectively reduced by 50% through representing it in single precision vs double precision (4 bytes vs 8 bytes per datum), all memory transfers and accesses should speed up as well – more if raw bandwidth is the main bottleneck, less so if the execution time is governed by latencies as the latter won't improve when a constant, small amount of data is accessed.

However, preliminary profiling of the benchmarking applications with NVIDIA's `nvprof` tooling already did not bode well, as double precision FPU usage was reported to be relatively low, on the arbitrary scale of `nvprof` a 3 out of 10. Furthermore, porting the benchmark runs quickly exposed further difficulties. The internal calculation of the convergence criteria in the AMG framework proved to be unreliable, as re-calculating it externally from the downloaded solution vector resulted in much higher numbers. In general, the AMG solvers did no longer reach the required residual – although reporting convergence – or did not converge at all for a number of specimens. The PBICGSTAB solver was especially affected by this, as it failed to return solutions for the regular cuboid at all resolutions, which are therefore missing in figure 4.9, which shows the performance gain the single precision solvers have over their double precision equivalents, as well as the PBICGSTAB-GMRES ratios for their single precision versions. As expected the single precision solvers need less time to compute solutions, but the ratios are far from the FPU ratio of 32:1. There are some good performance increases for the higher resolution specimens, in the best cases they only need half the time of their double precision runs.

However, as shown in figure 4.10, the quality of the solutions provided by the single precision solvers is not on par with the LINBCG baseline, the resulting residuals are one to two orders of magnitude above their double precision counterparts across all specimens. Since the LINBCG solver was originally validated and tuned with the well-known physical solution to the μ MAG #4 standard problem [24], it's questionable if the single precision solutions are numerically stable enough for use in physical, real-world applications.

Figure 4.9: Run time ratios of PBICGSTAB and GMRES operating on double precision (DP) vs single precision (SP) data, as well as their relative performance on single precision data. Since the PBICGSTAB solver runs on the cuboid specimens did not converge, there is also no run time ratio to show for them.

Figure 4.10: Mean absolute and relative residuals for the PBICGSTAB and GMRES solvers operating on single precision data in contrast to the LINBCG double precision baseline, which is represented by the dashed line. The left-right grouping of case studies is arbitrary and only meant to improve visual distinction. The single precision solver results are signified by the white horizontal (PBICGSTAB) or vertical (GMRES) bar overlaid on top of the case study marker. All single precision residuals are well above the dashed line for their respective case study, i.e. convergence at the required threshold was not actually reached. Compare also figure 3.3, which shows the same numbers for the double precision results, where the AMGX solvers are consistently below the threshold.

4.2.5 Consumer vs professional GPU comparison

In the same vein as the single precision solvers, one could also address the lack of double precision FPUs on the consumer Titan Xp by switching to professional, scientific-computing-oriented cards. To quantify the performance gains such cards offer, the same benchmarks as before were repeated on NVIDIA Tesla P100 cards. The different cards specifications and where they differ are described and discussed in detail in 3.3.

In isolation, the overall run time ratios for LINBCG, PBICGSTAB and GMRES compared to each other are similar to the results on the Titan Xp, PBICGSTAB is again outperforming all other solvers. The figure showing these run time ratios like figure 4.8 did for the Titan Xp is available in the appendix as figure A.1.

Figure 4.11: Run time ratios of PBICGSTAB on the Titan Xp in comparison to its performance on the P100.

However, comparing the PBICGSTAB run times on the P100 with those on the Titan Xp offers some insight how the mesh characterization metrics that were introduced can help to choose when the investment in much more costly professional cards might pay off, and when consumer cards are sufficient. Figure 4.11 shows that at high resolutions the sphere and irregular cuboid, which can be identified by their high distance to nearest neighbor values, profit disproportionately from solving them on the P100, nearly halving their run times as opposed to a run time decrease of only $\approx 20\%$ for the other case studies. This effect is even more pronounced on the V100, see figure A.2. Furthermore it's noticeable that across all case studies resolutions higher than 10^5 are necessary to gain any advantages from running the solver on the P100 at all.

Figure 4.12: Run time ratios of PBICGSTAB on the P100, comparing its performance on double precision data (DP) to that on single precision data (SP). There is no data for the cuboid case study, since the solver runs on these specimens did not converge in single precision representation.

Lastly, to confirm the conclusions drawn from the single precision benchmarks discussed in 4.2.4, namely that the arithmetic compute throughput is secondary to the impact of memory bandwidth, the single precision benchmarks were also run on the P100. If the double precision throughput were a significant performance bottleneck on the consumer-grade Titan Xp, one would expect to see much lower performance gains for the single precision runs on the professional P100, as the disparity in single vs double precision arithmetic throughput is much lower here. However, as can be seen in figure 4.12, the run time ratios are actually quite similar to the ones obtained on the consumer card which were shown in figure 4.9.

4.3 Sparse matrix vector multiplication microbenchmarks

To gain a deeper understanding of the underlying performance bottlenecks, the iterative solver binaries used for the benchmarks presented in 4.2 were profiled using `nvprof`, which reported that for all of them the majority of GPU kernel run time was spent on sparse matrix vector multiplication (SpMV) routines, which falls in line with the general approach of Krylov subspace methods as discussed in 2.2.2. For LINBCG that is an in-house TETRAMAG routine, specifically designed to take advantage of its custom reordered matrix representation, whereas the AMGX solvers use the CUSPARSE library routine `cusparseSpMV`, specifically and intentionally its `CSRMV_ALG2` variant¹.

Figure 4.13: Run times for 10^5 multiplications on the Titan Xp and the resulting run time ratios for the sparse matrix vector multiplication routines from TETRAMAG and the CUSPARSE vendor library.

To verify the advantage of `CSRMV_ALG2` in the AMGX library and investigate the benefits of the custom sparse matrix representation TETRAMAG uses, all three routines were benchmarked, the results are presented in figure 4.13. Contrary to the NVIDIA documentation [17], for high resolutions `CSRMV_ALG2` is here actually faster for the more regular case studies, and slightly slower than `CSRMV_ALG1` for the irregular ones. As the metrics presented in 4.1 can easily distinguish between these types of matrices, the AMGX solvers could benefit from choosing a concrete SpMV routine at run time based on the linear systems sparsity pattern.

¹See <https://github.com/NVIDIA/AMGX/commit/0e32e3568656200acfc1832ae82e6c79da0ee084>

Furthermore, the TETRAMAG sparse matrix memory scheme and multiplication routine are outperforming both vendor library implementations by a significant margin for all specimens with a resolution higher than $\approx 3 \cdot 10^4$ degrees of freedom. This in addition to the results presented in 4.2.4 emphasizes again the importance of memory bandwidth, memory latency and access patterns as the main bottleneck, as opposed to arithmetic throughput. However, the customized memory layout of the TETRAMAG sparse matrices might pose drawbacks in other algebraic operations which are needed by the solvers. If these would be offset by the performance gains from the sparse matrix vector multiplication alone, can't be answered without significant alterations to the AMGX code base and further research.

Figure 4.14: Run time ratios for the sparse matrix vector multiplication routines from TETRAMAG and CUSPARSE on the P100.

These micro benchmarks were repeated on the P100 cards as well, as their HBM2 memory architecture might behave differently. The resulting run time ratios are shown in figure 4.14, and in fact the CUSPARSE routines, especially CSR MV_ALG2, are losing less ground to the TETRAMAG routine than on the Titan Xp, which suggests that the higher memory bandwidth is able to compensate for the less efficient memory accesses.

Figure 4.15: Run time ratios for the CUSPARSE sparse matrix vector multiplication routine CSR MV_ALG2 on the Titan Xp over the P100.

Lastly, comparing the different cards directly in their `CSR MV_ALG2` performance in figure 4.15, there is a striking resemblance of figure 4.11, which compared the `PBICGSTAB` performance on both cards, underlining the importance and impact of this basic routine for the iterative solver approaches.

4.4 Direct solver results

Employing the factorization solver routines of the `CUSOLVER` library was partially successful. Both routines that were applied managed to deliver solutions for all case studies, but only at the lowest resolutions, as for the higher ones they either crashed as they were running out of memory, or returned unusable “solution” vectors with exceedingly high residuals. Where they did return an actual solution, they did so after vastly higher run times compared to all iterative solvers. Figure 4.16 shows that the direct solvers also exhibit an unfavourably steep run time scaling for higher resolutions.

Figure 4.16: Run times for a single solution for the decomposition solvers in comparison to the LINBCG baseline, as well as their run time ratios.

However, the solutions acquired by the direct solvers are much more accurate than any solutions from iterative approaches employed here, with absolute residuals of less than 10^{-4} and relative residuals of less than 10^{-14} , the solutions calculated by the direct solvers here are more than four orders of magnitude more precise than those of the iterative approaches. Still, as such high accuracy is usually not required, the prohibitively high run times discourage any application within the scope of this research.

Finally, the run time ratios between the two direct solvers also shown in figure 4.16 clearly indicate that in terms of run time, the Cholesky factorization routine is superior. It also managed to succeed in solving slightly larger linear systems than the **QR** decomposition routine for the regular and irregular cuboid case studies.

4.5 Conclusions

A new metric to identify sparsity patterns common to micromagnetic FEM simulations has been introduced. By calculating the mean distance to the nearest nonzero neighbor across all nonzero elements in a sparse matrix it is possible to differentiate between regular and irregular base meshes. This potentially allows to pre-select the time integrators and linear equation solvers used for the simulation of the magnetization dynamics.

A solver configuration based on the AMGX PBICGSTAB algorithm in combination with an AMG preconditioning has been identified as a general-purpose solution, which offers significant performance gains across all specimens studied compared to the TETRAMAG legacy solver implementation LINBCG. Through benchmarking solvers working on single precision data as well as analysis and micro-benchmarks of the underlying sparse matrix vector multiplication routines, empiric evidence has been provided that memory access patterns and memory bandwidth are the governing bottlenecks for the iterative solver's performance, while arithmetic double precision throughput is of less concern. Given that TETRAMAG's SpMV routine outperforms vendor implementations even a decade after it was written, customized matrix formats and routines specifically tailored to them promise significant performance gains if they could be applied to modern solver frameworks. However, even for the existing library routines, one could improve the solvers' performance by choosing an appropriate SpMV routine based on the mesh characterization metric that has been introduced.

By comparing benchmark results across a consumer vs a professional GPU, it was found that the sparsity pattern characterization metric can be used to identify on which types of linear systems the more costly investment in professional cards has a higher return on investment, namely on highly irregular meshes. Direct solver approaches based on decomposition algorithms were eliminated as candidates for current applications, based on them being vastly outperformed by iterative approaches.

Lastly, by performing the various benchmarks across a diverse set of case studies and scaling the problems in a way that allows for extrapolation, a baseline performance expectation for the different solvers and GPUs in the realm of micromagnetic FEM simulations has been recorded.

5 Summary and outlook

During the course of this research, I adapted several current frameworks to work in combination with the established TETRAMAG work flow, to prepare and examine a range of case studies, which I selected and designed based on the needs of physicists working with micromagnetic simulations on daily basis. By augmenting the existing codebase with sparse matrix format converters and benchmarking metrics I was able to directly compare the performance of a legacy sparse linear solver with those of several modern day implementations. I additionally modified these tools so that they also worked with single precision data. Furthermore, I adapted the resulting software stack to the requirements of an HPC cluster setting, allowing for exhaustive comparisons across a range of hardware platforms.

By setting up all the specimen data files along with the different benchmarking tools and their configurations through an automation pipeline, I was able to quickly iterate through the large number of available solver configurations in a consistent and reproducible fashion.

Through a series of profiling and microbenchmarks, I identified which hardware characteristics and specifications matter most for the solvers' performance, and how software needs to adapt to these limitations.

I analyzed the specimen matrices through different metrics, visual inspection and correlation to their performance impact on different numerical methods. I implemented a proof-of-concept routine to calculate the mean distance of all nonzero elements to their nearest nonzero neighbor in a matrix, which I found to be an accurate discriminator for the sparsity patterns the specimens exhibit. I put this distinguishing metric in context with the benchmark results obtained, and deduced several recommendations in which ways the performance of sparse linear system solvers could be improved by selecting appropriate methods and hardware based on the matrix' sparsity pattern.

The next steps in my work on future iterations of TETRAMAG will include applying the lessons learned from this work to the actual application, foremost by replacing the legacy LINBCG solver with the powerful PBICGSTAB implementation. I also hope to make some contributions to the upstream projects, such as including an option in the AMGX framework which allows to choose the sparse matrix vector multiplication routine during runtime.

Since I'm also working on some high level utilities to make micromagnetic simulations on HPC infrastructure more accessible through web-based interfaces, I would like to include the distance to nearest neighbor discriminator there to issue jobs to the appropriate consumer or professional GPU where both are available.

With the interdisciplinary input of the physicists I'm working with, development of more adapt residual metrics and convergence criteria used for the solvers based on physical necessity is a promising avenue for further research.

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A Supplementary results

A.1 NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU

Figure A.1: Run time ratios of PBICGSTAB, GMRES and LINBCG on the P100.

A.2 NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU

Figure A.2: Run time ratios of PBICGSTAB on the Titan Xp in comparison to its performance on the V100. This is the equivalent to figure 4.11.

Figure A.3: Run time ratios for the CUSPARSE sparse matrix vector multiplication routine CSRMV_ALG2 on the Titan Xp over the V100. This is the equivalent to figure 4.15.

A.3 P100 vs V100

Figure A.4: Run time ratios of PBICGSTAB on the P100 in comparison to its performance on the V100.

Figure A.5: Run time ratios for the CUSPARSE sparse matrix vector multiplication routine CSRMV_ALG2 on the P100 over the V100.

A.4 Absolute run times for all cards

Figure A.6: Absolute run times of PBICGSTAB on the three different GPU cards benchmarked.

B Gmsh geometry scripts

Case study	GMSH version	characteristic lengths
μ MAG #4	4.5.6	5, 4, 3, 2, 1.5, 1, 0.75, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4, 0.375
regular cuboid	4.5.6	8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3.5, 3, 2, 1.7, 1.5, 1.25
disk	3.0.6	3, 2.5, 2, 1.5, 1.25, 1, 0.8, 0.7, 0.65, 0.6, 0.55, 0.5
moebius	4.5.6	6, 5, 4, 3, 2.4, 2, 1.5, 1.2, 1, 0.8
sphere	4.5.6	4, 3.5, 3, 2.5, 2, 1.5, 1.25, 1, 0.9, 0.8, 0.75, 0.7, 0.65, 0.62
irregular cuboid	3.0.6	8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3.5, 3, 2, 1.7, 1.5, 1.25

Table B.1: The GMSH versions used for the case study meshes, along with the characteristic length parameters to generate all specimens.

Listing B.1: The script to generate the μ MAG #4 specimens. The characteristic lengths l_c used are given in table B.1.

```

1 lc = {{ lc }};
2
3 L = 500;
4 W = 125;
5 t = 3;
6 nx = L/lc;
7 ny = W/lc;
8 nz = 2;
9
10 p1 = newp; Point(p1) = {-L/2, -W/2, -t/2, lc};
11
12 l1[] = Extrude {L, 0, 0} {Point{p1}; Layers{nx}; };
13 s1[] = Extrude {0, W, 0} {Line{l1[1]}; Layers{ny}; };
14 ex1[] = Extrude {0, 0, t} {Surface{s1[1]}; Layers{nz}; };

```

Listing B.2: The script to generate the cuboid specimens. The characteristic lengths l_c used are given in table B.1.

```

1 lc = {{ lc }};
2
3 L = 500;
4 W = 125;
5 t = 50;
6 nx = L/lc;
7 ny = W/lc;

```

```

8  nz = t/lc;
9
10 p1 = newp; Point(p1) = {-L/2,-W/2,-t/2,lc};
11
12 l1[] = Extrude {L,0,0} {Point{p1}; Layers{nx}; };
13 s1[] = Extrude {0,W,0} {Line{l1[1]}; Layers{ny}; };
14 ex1[] = Extrude {0,0,t} {Surface{s1[1]}; Layers{nz}; };

```

Listing B.3: The script to generate the disk specimens. The characteristic lengths l_c used are given in table B.1.

```

1  lc = {{ lc }};
2
3  r = 50;
4  t = 20;
5  nz = t/lc;
6
7  center = newp; Point(center) = {0, 0, 0, lc};
8  top = newp; Point(top) = {r, 0, 0, lc};
9  right = newp; Point(right) = {0, r, 0, lc};
10 bottom = newp; Point(bottom) = {-r, 0, 0, lc};
11 left = newp; Point(left) = {0, -r, 0, lc};
12
13 l1 = newl;
14 Circle (l1) = {top, center, right};
15 l2 = newl;
16 Circle (l2) = {right, center, bottom};
17 l3 = newl;
18 Circle (l3) = {bottom, center, left};
19 l4 = newl;
20 Circle (l4) = {left, center, top};
21
22 l1 = newl1;
23 Line Loop(l1) = {l1, l2, l3, l4};
24
25 s = news;
26 Plane Surface(s) = {l1};
27
28 Extrude {0, 0, t} {Surface{s}; Layers{nz};}

```

Listing B.4: The script to generate the sphere specimens. The characteristic lengths l_c used are given in table B.1.

```
1 lc = {{ lc }};  
2  
3 SetFactory("OpenCASCADE");  
4 vol0 = newv;  
5 Sphere(vol0) = {0, 0, 0, 50};  
6 pts_vol0[] = PointsOf{Volume{vol0}};  
7 Characteristic Length{pts_vol0[]} = lc;
```

Listing B.5: The script to generate the irregular cuboid specimens. The characteristic lengths l_c used are given in table B.1.

```
1 lc = {{ lc }};  
2  
3 L = 500;  
4 W = 125;  
5 t = 50;  
6 nx = L/lc;  
7 ny = W/lc;  
8 nz = t/lc;  
9  
10 p1 = newp; Point(p1) = {-L/2, -W/2, -t/2, lc};  
11  
12 l1[] = Extrude {L, 0, 0} {Point{p1}};  
13 s1[] = Extrude {0, W, 0} {Line{l1[1]}};  
14 ex1[] = Extrude {0, 0, t} {Surface{s1[1]}};
```

C AMGX configurations

Listing C.1: AMGX configuration used for invoking the BICGSTAB solver. The “tolerance” was set as described in 3.2 to the values seen in figure 3.3.

```
1 {
2   "config_version": 2,
3   "solver": {
4     "solver": "BICGSTAB",
5     "print_solve_stats": 0,
6     "obtain_timings": 0,
7     "max_iters": 4000,
8     "monitor_residual": 1,
9     "convergence": "ABSOLUTE",
10    "scope": "main",
11    "tolerance": {{ tol }},
12    "norm": "L2"
13  }
14 }
```

Listing C.2: AMGX configuration used for invoking the PBICGSTAB solver. The “tolerance” was set as described in 3.2 to the values seen in figure 3.3.

```
1 {
2   "config_version": 2,
3   "exception_handling" : 1,
4   "solver": {
5     "print_grid_stats": 0,
6     "store_res_history": 0,
7     "solver": "PBICGSTAB",
8     "print_solve_stats": 0,
9     "obtain_timings": 0,
10    "preconditioner": {
11      "interpolator": "D2",
12      "print_grid_stats": 0,
13      "solver": "AMG",
14      "smoother": "JACOBI_L1",
15      "presweeps": 2,
16      "selector": "PMIS",
17      "coarsest_sweeps": 2,
18      "coarse_solver": "NOSOLVER",
19      "max_iters": 1,
20      "interp_max_elements": 4,
21      "min_coarse_rows": 2,
22      "scope": "amg_solver",
23      "max_levels": 24,
24      "cycle": "V",
25      "postsweeps": 2
26    },
27    "max_iters": 1000,
28    "monitor_residual": 1,
29    "convergence": "ABSOLUTE",
30    "tolerance": {{ tol }},
31    "norm": "L2"
32  }
33 }
```

Listing C.3: AMGX configuration used for invoking the GMRES solver. The “tolerance” was set as described in 3.2 to the values seen in figure 3.3.

```
1 {
2   "config_version": 2,
3   "exception_handling" : 1,
4   "solver": {
5     "print_grid_stats": 0,
6     "store_res_history": 0,
7     "solver": "GMRES",
8     "print_solve_stats": 0,
9     "obtain_timings": 0,
10    "preconditioner": {
11      "interpolator": "D2",
12      "print_grid_stats": 0,
13      "solver": "AMG",
14      "smoother": "JACOBI_L1",
15      "presweeps": 2,
16      "selector": "PMIS",
17      "coarsest_sweeps": 2,
18      "coarse_solver": "NOSOLVER",
19      "max_iters": 1,
20      "interp_max_elements": 4,
21      "min_coarse_rows": 2,
22      "scope": "amg_solver",
23      "max_levels": 24,
24      "cycle": "V",
25      "postsweeps": 2
26    },
27    "max_iters": 1000,
28    "monitor_residual": 1,
29    "gmres_n_restart": 10,
30    "convergence": "ABSOLUTE",
31    "tolerance": {{ tol }},
32    "norm": "L2"
33  }
34 }
```

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